

SYMPTOMS OF SYPHILIS IN WOMEN , METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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Abstract: *Syphilis (syphilis) is an infectious venereal disease, the causative agent of which is the infection of oozing treponema (spiroxeta). This micro organism is called whitish because it is poorly stained with aniline paint. The disease is transmitted sexually through the skin and mucous membranes. Direct contact and transmission through various types of household items are also mokin. The appearance of symptoms of syphilis is almost the same for men and women. The first sign of this disease is the appearance of a small inflamed wound, which can be mistaken for a simple bruise. The wound, which is called hard shankr, can be painless, even without paying attention to it. It appears at the site of entry of infectious pathogens, after 2-3 weeks after infection. Usually it bays are the genital area, chest, lips, tongue, face or fingers. The open surface of shankr poses a danger to others, because it is the source of infection. If the disease is not detected, the second stage of the disease develops. In 7-10 weeks, the syphilis ulcer or ulcer hardens, and the syphilis causative agent — treponema begins to penetrate into the blood and move throughout the body. Most often, the course of syphilis is confused with a simple colds, because syphilis is also accompanied by a lot of fatigue and intoxication. One of the reasons why it is difficult to diagnose correctly is the uncontrolled use of antibiotics. Under the influence of antibiotics, the disease is temporarily withdrawn, and people leave the appeal to the doctor late. The characteristic severe consequences of infection with syphilis occur in the third stage. Under the influence will be such important organs as the heart, circulatory system, spine and brain. And on the skin all sorts of rashes roseola, nodular rashes in Venereology such rashes are called papules. Men and women will have slightly different signs.*

Keywords: *Syphilis (syphilis) is an infectious venereal disease, oozing treponema (spiroxeta), severe chancre, roseola, nodular rash.*

Relevance of the topic: Symptoms of syphilis in women appear within 1-3 weeks after infection with oozing treponema. The time when the presence of the disease is not determined even by laboratory tests - the incubation period is from 3 weeks to 1 month. With some individual characteristics, this period can also be short. For example, if the body's immunity is weakened due to tuberculosis. If the patient for some reason took a large amount of antibacterial drugs before the infection, then this period lasts about

several months. The first signs of syphilis in women are the appearance of painless sores in the genital area or on the mucous membrane of the vagina and the appearance of itching around the vagina. Syphilis ulcer or severe chancre is another area of the skin, which can also appear on the back and neck of the uterus. There are also several manifestations of hard chancre, located in the distant parts of the body. Further development of the disease is accompanied by a rash on the entire body, as well as on the areas of the palms of the hands and feet. Painless swelling of the lymph nodes is observed after the infection has entered the lymph nodes. In the lymph nodes they multiply rapidly and spread throughout the body through the lymph. Densities appear in the mouth or around the anus. The appearance of severe chancre is due to the absence of pain, especially in women, they can not notice the disease in time. Another reason is that the wounds disappear by themselves, and its diameter can be small (~0.5 cm). Discomfort can only be caused by shankers, which are formed near the index finger nail or around the release hole in the back. Any unspecified rash on the skin can be signs of syphilis and can not be ignored. In order to timely identify the disease and get rid of serious consequences, it is necessary to consult with our doctors in due time.

Syphilis during pregnancy: Syphilis is very dangerous not only for the health of women, but also for the child to be born. In a mother infected with syphilis, a natural abortion (in the last stages of pregnancy) and a dead birth can occur. The child in the uterus is also at risk of infection with syphilis. In cases when syphilis is diagnosed during pregnancy, additional measures should be taken to avoid possible serious consequences. Two courses of treatment are mandatory. The first basic course of treatment is carried out in the hospital, the second course of treatment can be carried out in outpatient settings. Treatment is carried out with antibiotics and ceftrikason. For the treatment of syphilis, a special license must be issued to a private medical institution. At the end of the course of treatment, it is necessary to keep the medical report given for a long time, in which it will be written about the methods of treatment used in the treatment of the disease, as well as the types and dosages of drugs. Treatment is carried out with antibacterial drugs that do not have contraindications and do not affect the fetus. The presence of the disease is not an indication for the termination of pregnancy, it is possible to save the baby if necessary. Modern methods of treatment of this disease prevent infection. The disease ceases to develop, damage to internal organs and the central nervous system. The threat to the health of a pregnant woman is eliminated. Modern drugs prevent the transmission of the disease to the child by the affected mother, prevent congenital syphilis in children. Getting rid of the disease in the first half of pregnancy, a woman is considered safe for a child, etc., treatment of pregnant women is carried out in a specialized hospital.

Syphilis leads to the following complications: A person with syphilis first feels absolutely healthy, after 3-4 weeks (after the end of the latent-incubation period), the first sign of syphilis appears in the place where the whitish treponemes enter — the

aching primary syphiloma (severe shankr). If the patient is treated with an antibiotic due to furunculosis, inflammation of the lungs, angina, colic and other diseases, the latent period of syphilis can be quite prolonged. In such cases, the appropriate dose of antibiotics can not destroy treponemas, slightly inhibit their development, as a result of which, in addition to the fact that the latent period is quite prolonged, the disease can pass differently. With the appearance of severe shankr, the first period of syphilis begins: the lymph nodes close to the wound (shankr) are inflamed, swollen, enlarged and slightly stiffened; often the medicine dries up, the fever comes out, the head hurts, especially at night the bones hurt badly, weakness is observed. This period lasts 6-9 weeks and, if not treated in time, passes to the second period: large-small, colorful rash (purulent nodules) appears on the mucous membrane of the mouth, genitals, hands, feet and body with the appearance of spots, nodules and hakoza; in most patients, hair begins to shed, diseases of the bones, joints, muscles, blood vessels, heart, eyes, ears appear. Approximately after 3-5 years.

Conclusion: After getting rid of syphilis, it is necessary to avoid infectious diseases that can be transmitted in the future. The organism is not protected from the re-entry of the infection, it is necessary to remember this and take care to maintain health in a timely manner. The most effective method of protection is the mandatory use of a condom and the ability to choose a sexual companion to bypass.

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